

TRANSLATION OF THE TERMINOLOGY OF EMERGENCY SITUATIONS INTO UZBEK AND ITS ROLE IN TEACHING

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Abstract This article is dedicated to the analysis of the terminology of emergency situations as a complex terminological system, based on the expression of linguistic categories. The lexicon of emergency situations can be included among the newest terms that emerged at the turn of the 20th and 21st centuries. Its emergence is linked to several socio-linguistic factors: first, the complexity and diversity of the geographical landscape; second, the advanced level of the country's economic complex; and third, the necessity to take rapid actions with the help of various civil protection forces and means. Currently, descriptions of this lexicon are developed and reflected in several dictionaries. The special terminology of emergency situations has been formed in English and other languages.

Keywords: term, category, classification, terminology of emergency situations, nationalization, abbreviations.

INTRODUCTION

The developing society is increasingly facing risks and threats of both natural and technological character. Any military actions or the threats arising from them are having their effects. Specifically, in the national terminology of emergency situations (hereinafter referred to as ES terminology), the special unit of global disaster is noted, which “poses a threat to all of humanity and is associated with large-scale natural and technological impacts on the environment (e.g., military actions using ES, the fall of space objects to Earth, accidents in nuclear power plants, etc.)”. In this regard, almost all countries in the world and a number of international organizations are looking for more effective ways and methods to prevent accidents, disasters, and natural

calamities, as well as to eliminate their consequences. In this process, professional communication based on the standardized international terminology of emergency situations plays a crucial role.

The above-mentioned circumstances highlight the relevance of categorizing (classifying) the terminology of emergency situations. An analysis of modern terminological research shows that the study of ES terminology in national terminologies, particularly the issues related to its semantic concept and classification opportunities, has not been fully explored. Studying the terminology of emergency situations in terms of its specific semantic, structural, and conceptual characteristics is scientifically urgent and promising.

According to V.M. Leychik's proposed chronology, "Terminology has gone through four stages of development and has reached its fifth stage. This stage is characterized by the changing place of terminology in the system of modern sciences... Cognitive terminology has emerged...". Many scholars, based on this statement, refer to this period as the cognitive era. For example, V.F. Novodranova writes: "Terminology has entered its cognitive development phase and must revisit its traditional questions regarding the essence of a term... it raises new problems about language for special purposes, the conceptual structures behind the term, professional communication, and cognitive maps of science".

The central issue in cognitive terminology is the relationship between language units (terms) and the professional knowledge structures they embody (a collection of concepts unified by a specific hierarchy, objectified in the term). Terminology is seen as the result of specialists' cognitive activity, involving the conceptualization and verbalization of knowledge. The level of conceptualization depends on the level of existing knowledge, the terminology system where the term should be introduced, and the professional and linguistic competencies of the specialists. In these processes,

language plays a significant role, determining how the human mind perceives and categorizes the world, as well as how it objectifies those perceptions.

Yu.V. Slojenikina defines terminology as the spontaneous formation of specialized words resulting from the collection and understanding of knowledge in a certain area of activity. Terminology becomes systematic when the core concepts and relationships between them are described in a meta-language. The formation of systematization in terminology is directly influenced by two key processes—categorization and conceptualization—as a result of human terminological creativity and cognitive thinking.

In the context of the cognitive-communicative paradigm, categorization is considered a dynamic process that links a particular concept with a specific linguistic sign within speech-thought activity. Categorization in this sense involves cognitive and mental processes, reflecting the conceptual structures and principles of cognitive classification.

METHODOLOGY

The research material consists of terms related to emergency situations and humanitarian assistance from American, British, and Russian printed and electronic sources. Notable works include Robert Stafford's "Disaster Relief and Emergency Assistance Act (USA)", the "Lexicon of UK Civil Protection Terminology" (UK), V.A. Puchkov's "Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief", and others. These works have contributed to the theoretical and methodological basis of this study. The study of emergency situations terminology is an essential component of language for specific purposes, and it draws from both traditional approaches and the achievements of cognitive and communicative linguistics. This requires employing semantic, cognitive, and functional research methods.

The semantic issues discussed in the article relate to identifying the unique semes in the structure of the terms under study, dividing them into lexical-semantic groups, and analyzing their polysemy and metaphorical layers. Cognitive aspects enable the identification of the cognitive properties behind these terms, while the functional approach addresses the ways in which people use these specialized signs in professional communication and how they contribute to achieving effective communication in practice.

ANALYSIS

Naturally, emergencies have both international and national characteristics, and the terminology associated with emergencies is linguistically diverse. For instance, in the English language, emergency terminology includes prefixes derived from Greek and Latin, such as: *post-disaster activities* (activities carried out after a disaster), *pre-disaster activities* (activities conducted before a disaster), and *post-emergency activities* (actions taken after an emergency). Additionally, English emergency terminology incorporates borrowings from widely spoken languages, primarily French (e.g., *rescuer*, *accident*, *hazard*) and from Asian languages, such as *lahar* (muddy lava, Indonesia) and *bei* (rainy season, Japan). The Japanese term *tsunami* has even become an international term within emergency response vocabulary. This vocabulary exhibits characteristics common to international medical terminology, including a high prevalence of Greek-Latin derived terms (e.g., *osteosynthesis*) and numerous eponyms (e.g., *Whitman's plaster bandage*)

In emergency medical terminology, the existence of synonyms and variants (e.g., *blow*, *hit*, *stroke*, *strike*) and polysemous terms indicates the constant evolution of medical science and practice. Scientific language is not "dry," and medical terminology is no exception. The anthropocentric nature of language means that the term creation process is influenced by the author's associations. The field of emergency medicine contains many metaphorical terms, which do not hinder professional communication (e.g., *stuck heel sign*, *key sign*).

A distinctive feature of emergency terminology is its conceptual basis, which often involves interdisciplinary polysemy due to the complex nature of this theoretical and practical field. For example, the term *debris* has several meanings in different fields: 1) rock fragments (geology); 2) pathological deposits (medicine); 3) construction waste or landslides (construction). This form of polysemy, as well as the widespread use of common vocabulary, complicates precise interpretation. For example, the term *action* is broadly used across various fields and can be interpreted differently in different contexts, such as in *evacuation actions* or *action for damages*.

As systems of specialized language evolve, they develop in a living and dynamic manner. One form of linguistic development is abbreviation—creating secondary shortened forms to refer to specific realities. In terms of language economy, abbreviations allow speakers to convey meaning in a minimal and efficient manner. As noted by Y.V. Slogenkina, the principle behind abbreviation is to express a specific concept in the fewest possible words.

Abbreviations and acronyms are common in emergency terminology. For example, *MSF* (Médecins Sans Frontières, "Doctors Without Borders") and *EMERCOM* (a Russian acronym for the Ministry of Civil Defence, Emergencies, and the Elimination of Consequences of Natural Disasters, which in English refers to the Ministry of the Russian Federation for Civil Defence, Emergencies, and the Elimination of Natural Disaster Consequences). These terms reflect the development and structure of emergency-related communication in a highly specialized context.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The terminology system under analysis is characterized by its complex thematic structure, which relates to the various types of emergency situations, the actions taken to mitigate them, and the involvement of human resources and technical tools. According to S.V. Grinev, when discussing the formation and development of terminology, one must distinguish between different types of specialized units: primary ones, which are initially adopted from the relevant subject-concept domain

of the national language, and those that are borrowed from other knowledge areas. The terminology of emergency situations has a complex nature, integrating specialized terms from various fields such as military, medical, legal, technical, engineering, transport, environmental, biological, geological, physical, chemical, meteorological, sociological, psychological, marine, aviation, computer science, and economics. Given this linguistic status, it is appropriate to apply categorical analysis to study the specific features of this terminology system.

By analyzing the terms from several categories, the article illustrates their distinctive features and demonstrates how categorization facilitates understanding the interconnectedness of terms across different domains. For instance, the term “accident” includes multiple terms that reflect various ontological perspectives, such as industrial accident, radiation accident, ecological accident, and others. These terms, though distinct, belong to a single terminological system and are interconnected semantically and lexically.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, understanding the categories within the terminology of emergency situations, their semantic relationships, and the lexical features of these terms is crucial for accurately translating and applying these terms in professional contexts. The systematic categorization of emergency situations terminology also enhances our ability to improve the terminology system and contribute to more precise translations, particularly from English to Uzbek.

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